

Synergistic extraction of cerium(III)-oxinates in presence of tributyl phosphine oxide

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Abstract : Synergistic effect of tributyl phosphine oxide (TBPO) on the liquid-liquid extraction of cerium(III) with oxine and 2-methyl oxine into various organic solvents has been described. The metal ion was labeled by ^{141}Ce radiotracer and determined by its characteristics γ -energy. The nature of extracted species, their compositions and extraction equilibria were derived from distribution data. The effects of different solvents on the extent of synergism have been explained by the application of theory of regular solution.

Keywords : Synergistic extraction, ^{141}Ce , oxine and 2-methyl oxine, tributyl phosphine oxide.

Introduction

The phenomenon in which two extractants present together, extract species, mostly metal ions, with greater efficiency than that corresponding to their additive action is called synergism. While one of the extractant satisfies the charge of the metal ion, other saturates its co-ordination shell resulting it as much hydrophobic as possible. Thus, two extractants fulfill different objectives in the extraction process and thereby co-operate to yield partitioning that is higher than the sum of each extractant operating independently. Among the different classes of synergistic combinations, most versatile and widely studied one is the mixture of a chelating agent and a neutral donor, termed as synergists¹⁻³. Large enhancement in extraction in such cases has been widely investigated from the theoretical, analytical and applied point of view.

The extent of synergism of any set of mixture of extractants depends on several factors e.g. structure of chelating agents⁴, basicity of donor molecules⁵, size of central atom⁶, and also in particular, nature of diluents⁷. Arichi *et al.*⁸ reported that only diluents containing polar groups yield fairly high distribution co-efficient and aromatic compounds exhibit more efficient extraction than aliphatic compounds⁹. Such diluent effect was attributed to the formation of ternary adduct in organic phase, the stability of which in turn might direct the course of synergistic extraction. The distribution co-efficients of reac-

tants are very much influenced by the physicochemical properties of the solvent, since the activity co-efficient of a chemical species are sensitive to the medium. From Hildebrand's regular solution theory¹⁰, activity co-efficient of reacting species in different media can be calculated using the knowledge of solubility parameters of species taking part in extraction process and subsequently, adduct formation constants may be evaluated. Thus, a direct correlation of the solvent with the extent of synergism is possible.

Another important factor in synergistic extraction is the effect of temperature. From the measured values of thermodynamic parameters e.g. ΔH_f^0 , ΔS_f^0 , ΔG_f^0 etc. through the variation of extraction temperature, it is possible to elucidate the extraction pathway¹¹. Thus transfer of hard cations like Np^{4+} by the combination of HPBI and TOPO was found¹² to be highly enthalpy favoured via expansion of co-ordination shell of the metal but steric crowding around the small cation (0.98 Å) by four isooxazolone moiety might lead to large loss of entropy. However, ΔG_f^0 values for both the binary and ternary extractions were negative showing spontaneous nature of extractions.

In the present work, extraction of Ce^{III} from a hydrochloric acid medium by 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine) and 2-methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline (2-methyl oxine) into different organic solvents were investigated. The enhance-

ment effect of tri butyl phosphine oxide (TBPO) on such extraction processes have been studied in terms of the variation of parameters like pH, extraction concentration, temperature etc. Although, a wide number of mixed-extraction of lanthanide elements are found in literature¹³, systematic studies with cerium(III) is less common¹⁴. The role of diluents on the extent of extraction was also investigated by the application of Hildebrand's regular solution theory.

Results and discussion

Extraction with individual ligands and synergistic extractant :

Both binary and ternary extractions of Ce^{III} from aqueous chloride media, kept at pH 3, were studied in terms of ligand concentration on the distribution ratio (D_0 and D_{mix} represents the corresponding values for individual ligand and mixture of ligand and donor respectively). pH of aqueous solution was optimized by initial pH variation with both the two ligands and fixed at pH 3 for subsequent experiments.

In cases of both of two ligands, extractions were found to increase with increase in ligand concentration (Figs. 1, 2). This may be explained by the release of the more water molecules by the ligand from the inner sphere of metal ion, a fact immediate consequence of better coordinating ability of chelating agent oxine and 2-methyl oxine than water. However, pure donor TBPO extracts the metal

Fig. 1. Variation of distribution ratio (D_0) of Ce^{III} with oxine concentration in different solvents.

Fig. 2. Variation of distribution ratio (D_0) of Ce^{III} with 2-methyl oxine concentration in different solvents.

to a very negligible extent addition of donor to the binary mixture, enhances the distribution ratio appreciably (Figs. 3, 4), perhaps due to replacement of residual water by donor rendering the ternary adduct more organophilic. The effect is more pronounced in case of 2-methyl oxine than pure oxine, owing to +I effect of methyl group, making lone pair on nitrogen atom more available for co-ordination.

Fig. 3. The plot of $\log [D_{mix} - D_0]$ vs $\log [oxine]$ in synergistic extraction of Ce^{III} in presence of fixed concentration of TBPO in different solvents, concentration of TBPO = $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Fig. 4. The plot of $\log [D_{\text{mix}} - D_0]$ vs $\log [2\text{-methyl oxine}]$ in synergistic extraction of Ce^{III} in presence of fixed concentration of TBPO in different solvents, concentration of TBPO = $1.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

The parameter governing the synergistic effect known as synergistic co-efficient (S.C.) and apparent formation constant (β) of adduct are defined by¹⁶,

$$\text{S.C.} = \log (D_{\text{mix}} / D_0 + D_s), D_s = 0 \text{ (here)}$$

$$\beta (\text{mol}^{-1}) = D_{\text{mix}} - D_0 / D_0 [\text{TBPO}]$$

Experimentally determined values of these two parameters (Tables 1–4) reflect that the solvent has an important role in adduct formation reaction, as they are found

Table 1. Synergistic extraction of Ce^{III} in presence of fixed concentration of TBPO ($1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) with varying concentration oxine in different solvents

Solvents	Concentration of oxine $[M] \times 10^{-3}$				
	D_0	D_{mix}	S.C.	$\log \beta$	
Xylene	0.5	0.69	0.14	2.50	
	1.0	5.36	0.19	2.64	
	1.5	19.94	0.18	2.61	
	2.0	50.23	0.18	2.61	
	2.5	146.61	0.17	2.57	
Cyclohexane	0.5	0.24	0.05	1.97	
	1.0	1.46	0.04	1.94	
	1.5	4.25	0.05	1.95	
	2.0	7.50	0.05	2.01	
	2.5	13.82	0.06	2.04	
Isoamyl alcohol	0.5	5.60	0.03	1.68	
	1.0	20.25	0.02	1.59	
	1.5	71.17	0.02	1.68	

Table-1 (contd.)

Carbon tetra chloride	2.0	171.59	181.89	0.02	1.68
	2.5	537.40	568.59	0.02	1.66
	0.5	4.57	4.77	0.02	1.53
	1.0	17.41	18.16	0.02	1.53
	1.5	59.54	61.93	0.02	1.51
Toluene	2.0	147.20	153.18	0.02	1.51
	2.5	395.37	411.62	0.02	1.51
	0.5	0.43	2.66	0.78	3.62
	1.0	3.32	13.91	0.62	3.41
	1.5	12.16	53.15	0.64	3.43
	2.0	14.07	54.27	0.58	3.36
	2.5	35.86	147.50	0.61	3.40

S.C. = $\log (D_{\text{mix}} / D_0 + D_s)$, $\beta (\text{mol}^{-1}) = D_{\text{mix}} - D_0 / D_0 [\text{TBPO}]$.

Table 2. Synergistic extraction of Ce^{III} in presence of fixed concentration of oxine ($0.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) with varying concentration TBPO in different solvents

Solvents	Concentration of TBPO $[M] \times 10^{-3}$				
	D_0	D_{mix}	S.C.	$\log \beta$	
Xylene	0.7	0.84	0.09	2.48	
	1.0	0.91	0.12	2.52	
	1.2	0.69	0.14	2.50	
	1.5	1.01	0.17	2.50	
	1.7	1.04	0.18	2.47	
Cyclohexane	0.7	0.26	0.03	2.04	
	1.0	0.27	0.04	2.00	
	1.2	0.24	0.05	1.97	
	1.5	0.27	0.05	1.92	
	1.7	0.28	0.05	1.90	
Isoamyl alcohol	0.7	5.73	0.01	1.51	
	1.0	5.79	0.01	2.16	
	1.2	5.60	0.02	2.40	
	1.5	5.95	0.02	2.42	
	1.7	5.99	0.02	2.47	
Carbon tetra chloride	0.7	4.70	0.01	1.58	
	1.0	4.73	0.01	1.56	
	1.2	4.57	0.01	1.54	
	1.5	4.80	0.02	1.52	
	1.7	4.83	0.02	1.51	
Toluene	0.7	2.43	0.74	3.79	
	1.0	2.25	0.71	3.62	
	1.2	0.43	2.66	0.78	3.62
	1.5	2.98	0.83	3.66	
	1.7	3.25	0.87	3.57	

S.C. = $\log (D_{\text{mix}} / D_0 + D_s)$, $\beta (\text{mol}^{-1}) = D_{\text{mix}} - D_0 / D_0 [\text{TBPO}]$.

Table 3. Synergistic extraction of Ce^{III} in presence of fixed concentration of TBPO ($1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$) with varying concentration 2-methyl oxine in different solvents

Solvents	Concentration of 2-methyl oxine				
	[M] × 10 ⁻⁴	D ₀	D _{mix}	S.C.	log β
Chloroform	0.5	5.39	13.56	0.40	4.08
	1.0	43.68	112.31	0.41	4.09
	1.5	176.64	455.30	0.41	4.10
	2.0	445.96	1122.28	0.40	4.08
	2.5	853.49	2194.32	0.41	4.10
Cyclohexane	0.5	0.75	0.85	0.05	3.02
	1.0	3.62	4.06	0.05	2.99
	1.5	9.28	10.46	0.05	3.01
	2.0	25.70	29.10	0.05	3.03
	2.5	48.63	55.07	0.05	3.02
Isoamyl alcohol	0.5	3.06	3.54	0.06	3.10
	1.0	20.19	23.66	0.07	3.14
	1.5	93.69	110.08	0.07	3.15
	2.0	262.36	304.02	0.06	3.10
	2.5	449.99	520.24	0.06	3.10
Carbon tetra chloride	0.5	4.19	4.39	0.02	2.57
	1.0	32.53	33.88	0.02	2.52
	1.5	136.84	142.63	0.02	2.53
	2.0	351.64	367.37	0.02	2.56
	2.5	648.34	678.89	0.02	2.58
Toluene	0.5	0.95	1.04	0.04	2.89
	1.0	3.03	3.39	0.04	2.98
	1.5	15.77	17.51	0.04	2.94
	2.0	39.91	44.39	0.04	2.95
	2.5	126.21	139.99	0.04	2.94

S.C. = $\log (D_{\text{mix}}/D_0 + D_s)$, $\beta (\text{mol}^{-1}) = D_{\text{mix}} - D_0/D_0 [\text{TBPO}]$.

Table 4. Synergistic extraction of Ce^{III} in presence of fixed concentration of 2-methyl oxine ($0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$) with varying concentration TBPO in different solvents

Solvents	Concentration of TBPO				
	[M] × 10 ⁻⁴	D ₀	D _{mix}	S.C.	log β
Chloroform	0.7		10.52	0.29	4.13
	1.0		11.43	0.32	4.05
	1.2	5.39	13.56	0.40	4.10
	1.5		15.96	0.47	4.11
	1.7		19.82	0.56	4.19
Cyclohexane	0.7		0.81	0.03	3.04
	1.0		0.83	0.04	3.03
	1.2	0.75	0.85	0.05	3.04
	1.5		0.87	0.06	3.03

Table-4 (contd.)

	1.7		0.88	0.07	3.04
Isoamyl alcohol	0.7		3.39	0.04	3.20
	1.0		3.44	0.05	3.10
	1.2	3.06	3.54	0.06	3.11
	1.5		3.59	0.06	3.06
	1.7		3.66	0.07	3.06
Carbon tetra chloride	0.7		4.33	0.01	2.67
	1.0		4.36	0.01	2.60
	1.2	4.19	4.39	0.01	2.59
	1.5		4.43	0.02	2.57
	1.7		4.47	0.02	2.58
Toluene	0.7		1.02	0.03	3.06
	1.0		1.04	0.03	2.98
	1.2	0.95	1.04	0.04	2.90
	1.5		1.05	0.04	2.86
	1.7		1.07	0.05	2.89

S.C. = $\log (D_{\text{mix}}/D_0 + D_s)$, $\beta (\text{mol}^{-1}) = D_{\text{mix}} - D_0/D_0 [\text{TBPO}]$.

to vary widely for different solvents. For ternary complex of oxine, highest synergistic effect is reported in toluene while for 2-methyl oxine, corresponding solvent is chloroform. It is interesting to note that in binary extraction with 2-methyl oxine, chloroform exhibit maximum extraction, but for oxine, best solvent is iso amyl alcohol. In all cases appreciable synergic effect is observed which in turn again may be designated as diluent dependent process.

Nature of extracted species :

The plot of logarithm of distribution ratios' for both binary and ternary extractions against the concentration of each kind, used separately, yielded straight line of slope ~3 for all of the five diluents (Figs. 1-4). This implies the involvement of three bidentated chelating groups around the cation in both binary and ternary extraction. Assuming D_0 and D_{mix} as the corresponding values of distribution ratios, following equations are derivable,

$$\log k = \log D_0 - 3 \log [\text{HA}] - 3\text{pH} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\log K = \log (D_{\text{mix}} - D_0) - 3 \log [\text{HA}] - \log [\text{S}] - 3\text{pH} \quad (2)$$

Where equilibrium constants for binary and ternary extractions are k and K respectively and $[\text{HA}]$ and $[\text{S}]$ are concentration of undissociated ligand and donor molecule.

As, slope ratio analysis shows that only one donor molecule is involved in ternary extraction (Figs. 5, 6) and TBPO extracts the metal ion only to a poor extent in case of individual extraction, formula of ternary adduct in mixed extraction is considered to be $[CeA_3S]$ and its overall formation constant K_s is given by

$$\log K_s = \log K - \log k \quad (3)$$

All these eq. (1)–(3) are found to be equally valid for

Fig. 5. The plot of $\log [D_{\text{mix}} - D_0]$ vs $\log [TBPO]$ in synergistic extraction of Ce^{III} in presence of fixed concentration of oxine in different solvents, concentration of ligand = $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Fig. 6. The plot of $\log [D_{\text{mix}} - D_0]$ vs $\log [TBPO]$ in synergistic extraction of Ce^{III} in presence of fixed concentration of 2-methyl oxine in different solvents, concentration of ligand = $0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$.

both of the two ligands e.g. oxine and 2-methyl oxine dissolved in different organic solvents. Experimentally determined values of equilibrium constants (k , K and K_s) are shown in Tables 5 and 6. Results reflect the formation of relatively strong ternary adduct in organic phase for oxine complexes in toluene medium and for 2-methyl oxine complexes in chloroform medium. The same was observed in the case of determination of degree of synergism (Tables 1–4). Another point which must be explained for the experimentally determined equilibrium constant of Ce^{III} that 2-methyl oxine forms stronger complexes,

Table 5. Equilibrium constants for binary and ternary systems of Ce^{III} -oxine

System	Binary system		Ternary system	
	Solvent	$\log K$	Donor	$\log K_s$
Ce^{III} -oxine	Xylene	6.01	TBPO	8.59 2.57
	Cyclohexane	5.01	7.03	2.02
	Isoamyl alcohol	5.58	8.24	2.67
	Carbon tetra chloride	6.44	7.96	1.52
	Toluene	5.40	8.80	3.40

Table 6. Equilibrium constants for binary and ternary systems of Ce^{III} -2-methyl oxine

System	Binary system		Ternary system	
	Solvent	$\log K$	Donor	$\log K_s$
Ce^{III} -	Chloroform	9.78	TBPO	13.88 4.10
2-methyl oxine	Cyclohexane	8.53	11.56	3.03
	Isoamyl alcohol	9.50	12.60	3.10
	Carbon tetra chloride	9.66	12.23	2.58
	Toluene	8.95	11.89	2.94

perhaps due to +I effect of methyl group in former, making the lone pair of nitrogen more available for coordination.

Temperature effect :

Temperature effect is the most complex factor affecting the synergistic extraction process. The influence of temperature on distribution ratio's were studied with the ligands separately in different organic solvents and also in presence of donor (TBPO), keeping concentration of Ce^{III} and extractant constants constant. The change in enthalpy (ΔH^0), entropy (ΔS^0) and free energy (ΔG^0) of each of the extraction system were evaluated using¹⁵

$$\log K = \frac{-\Delta H_f^0}{2.303 RT} + \frac{-\Delta S_f^0}{2.303 R} \quad (4)$$

The plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ yields a straight line. ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 can be calculated from the intercept of the straight line. Such results are shown in Figs. 7, 8 and calculated values of the parameters are shown in Tables 7, 8. Negative values of ΔG^0 in all cases indicate the extraction

Fig. 7. Effect of temperature on the extraction constant of Ce^{III} with oxine in presence of TBPO into different solvents.

Fig. 8. Effect of temperature on the extraction constant of Ce^{III} with 2-methyl oxine in presence of TBPO into different solvents.

processes to be spontaneous and take place in forward directions. As the metal ion Ce^{III} itself is hard acid and the two ligands contain hard donor center (O, N) complex formation involve hard-hard interaction, as per Pearson's HSAB principle. Such interactions are charac-

Table 7. Thermodynamic parameters related to ternary system of the metal complex Ce^{III} -Oxine

System	Solvent	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Ce^{III} -oxine-	Xylene	70.20	397.28	-48.19
TBPO	Cyclohexane	223.04	883.10	-40.10
	Isoamyl alcohol	70.07	392.90	-47.01
	Carbon tetra chloride	49.98	315.83	-44.14
	Toluene	80.19	436.89	-49.99

Table 8. Thermodynamic parameters related to ternary system of the metal complex Ce^{III} -2-methyl oxine

System	Solvent	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Ce^{III} -2-	Chloroform	43.83	412.62	-79.14
methyl oxine-	Cyclohexane	32.55	330.14	-65.83
TBPO	Isoamyl alcohol	18.91	303.67	-71.58
	Carbon tetra chloride	35.81	302.75	-54.41
	Toluene	27.98	321.27	-67.76

terized by positive values of enthalpy and entropy changes (Tables 7, 8). Enthalpy changes are positive which indicate bond breaking takes place, due to replacement of water molecules present in the inner sphere of metal by the donor molecule in course of ternary adduct formation. As such, release of large no. of water molecules results increase the degrees of freedom, accompanied by gain in entropy. Experimental data in Tables 7, 8 support the mechanism of mixed extraction and this is applicable for both of the two ligands. Hence, the synergistic effect of TBPO on the extraction of Ce^{III} by oxine and 2-methyl oxine can be regarded as 'entropy' - driven but enthalpy disfavoured process.

Effect of diluents :

The process synergism may be described as the rise in extent of extraction by addition of a neutral donor into metal-chelate complex, forming ternary adducts in organic solvents. Results in Tables 1-4 established that the diluent has an important role in deciding the degree of synergism which varies widely with the nature of organic solvents. Such variation of synergistic effect cannot be explain⁷ by the dielectric constants of solvents. However Hildebrand's regular solution theory can be applied to explore the nature of the solvents controlling the extent

of synergism. In several previous investigations^{15–20} application of this concept had been made successfully. From regular solution theory, it has been possible to calculate the activity and activity co-efficient of interacting species with the aid of the knowledge of solubility parameters and molar volumes. Accordingly adduct formation constant K_s is related to the solubility parameter of diluent by²¹

$$\log K_s = 2B \delta_{\text{org}} + \text{constant} \quad (5)$$

where,

$$B = 1/2.303 RT [V_{\text{adduct}} \cdot \delta_{\text{adduct}} - V_{\text{chelate}} \cdot \delta_{\text{chelate}} - V_{\text{donor}} \cdot \delta_{\text{donor}}] \quad (6)$$

and, V = molar volumes of adduct, chelate and donor, δ = solubility parameter of adduct, chelate and donor.

Both V and δ depends on diluents nature and constant term is independent on diluents.

In the present investigation, experimentally determined $\log K_s$ in each solvent is plotted against solubility parameters (δ_{org}) of respective diluents (Fig. 9) and the slope of resulting straight line was equated to ' $2B$ ' from which δ_{adduct} was calculated using above relation. Solubility parameter of the ternary adduct was also calculated theoretically adopting a previous method¹⁵. A comparison of

Fig. 9. The plot of $\log K_s$ vs δ_{org} in synergistic extraction of Ce^{III} in different diluents.

δ_{adduct} values in Table 9 obtained theoretically and experimentally for two types of ternary complexes involving oxine and 2-methyl oxine establishes the validity of the regular solution theory in these systems.

Table 9. Solubility parameter (δ_{adduct}) of Ce^{III} -oxinate-TBPO as ternary system

Ligand	δ_{adduct} ($\text{J}^{1/2} \text{cm}^{-3/2}$)	
	Theoretical	Present work
Oxine	13.82	13.43 ± 0.01
2-Methyl oxine	12.10	12.74 ± 0.01

Experimental

Reagents :

Stock solution of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving A.R. Ceric ammonium nitrate in deionised water. It was reduced with oxalic acid and finally dissolved in dilute HCl and spiked with ^{141}Ce radiotracer, supplied by BRIT, Mumbai, India. The strength working solution of the metal ion was kept $\sim 10^{-4}$ (M) by appropriate dilution. The two chelating agents oxine and 2-methyl oxine and donor TBPO (A.R.) were obtained from M/s Sigma-Aldrich, USA. All the organic diluents used in present study were purified by standard procedures. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Apparatus :

Radioactivity of Ce-141 was measured at its 145 keV photopeak using a single channel γ -ray spectrometer coupled with a well-type NaI (TI) detector of Nucleonix, India make. A Systronics model 335 digital pH-meter was used to pH measurement.

Solvent extraction procedure :

For the distribution studies, previous method¹⁵ was adopted. Equal volumes (5 mL each) of aqueous and organic phases existing of metal ion solution and ligand respectively were equilibrated in a mechanical shaker for a period of 30 min keeping pH of aqueous phase fixed at 3.00. After equilibration 1 mL each of two phases were separately measured their radio activities. From which distribution ratio were computed in usual way.

$$D = \frac{\text{Radioactivity in organic phase}}{\text{Radioactivity in aqueous phase}}$$

For mixed extraction study, appropriate amount of donor TBPO was added to the organic phase.

Conclusions

The overall investigation deals with the effect of temperature and diluents on the formation of Ce^{III} -oxinates/

2-methyl oxinates/TBPO adduct. Regular solution theory is applicable for both of the two systems. On the other hand, evaluation of thermodynamic parameters advocates in favour of inner sphere complex formation in case of the both of the two ligands, although 2-methyl oxine forms somewhat strong complex than its oxine counterpart.

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